
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON FLUID MOTION OF WATER VORTEX FOLLOWING KEPLER'S LAWS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to verify through physical experiments whether the fluid motion laws in a water vortex system conform to Kepler's laws of planetary motion. Specifically, by quantitatively analyzing the orbital parameters of rotating spheres in the vortex, it examines the applicability of Kepler's third law (under the approximation of circular orbits, the ratio of the cube of the orbital radius to the square of the period is a constant) in fluid mechanics scenarios. It also explores the potential of water vortices as a macroscopic physical model for simulating the laws of celestial body motion. The experiment preliminarily confirms that the water vortex and the Keplerian system follow the unified vortex dynamics law of the central force field, namely

$$\frac{R^3}{T^2} = K$$

where K is the Keplerian constant characterizing the water vortex system.

Keywords Water Vortex; Kepler's Laws; Machine Vision; Fluid Motion

1 Introduction

Inspired by the universality of Kepler's laws in celestial systems, this study attempts to apply machine vision technology (industrial camera + VisionMaster software) to water vortex dynamics experiments, exploring the isomorphism between fluid motion and celestial motion through the following approaches:

- **Quantitative Verification:** Using a magnetic stirrer to generate stable axisymmetric water vortices, measuring orbital parameters of multiple sets of suspended balls, and analyzing the degree of coincidence between the R^3/T^2 ratio and Kepler's third law, so as to provide experimental evidence for whether there are orbital laws similar to celestial bodies in fluid systems.
- **Method Optimization:** Aiming at the problem of vortex stability in traditional research, a dual screening strategy of "trajectory repeatability constraint method" and "energy conservation verification method" is proposed, providing a new technical path for vortex energy monitoring in dynamic equilibrium.
- **Model Expansion:** If the experiment is verified, the water vortex system can be used as a macroscopic physical model with both cost-effectiveness and visualization advantages, providing a supplementary reference framework for the teaching demonstration and theoretical research of celestial motion laws.

2 Experimental Methods

2.1 Experimental Setup and Observation Methods

A magnetic stirrer was used to generate a stable axisymmetric water vortex. A yellow floating ball (Ball C) was placed at the center of the vortex as the central reference point, and red (Ball A) and blue (Ball B) floating balls

were symmetrically arranged in the periphery as orbital observation objects. The motion trajectories of the balls were real-time captured by a machine vision system (equipped with an industrial camera, model: MV-CU120-10GC, with the lens vertically 50.0 cm away from the water surface). The distance data between the centers of the two balls and Ball C were recorded by VisionMaster software (Version: V5.3.1) at a frequency of 4.0 ± 0.1 frames per second, so as to analyze the motion trajectories of Ball A (red) and Ball B (blue) in the vortex plane through pixel coordinates.

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2.3 Screening of Vortex Samples

The experiment requires a stable vortex with essentially constant energy. A stable vortex refers to one with minimal energy change per unit time, similar to a figure skater spinning on ice, which maintains short-term angular momentum conservation without extra assistance. However, for water vortices, due to the high viscosity of water, the energy dissipates extremely rapidly and the rotation speed drops sharply once the magnetic stirrer stops rotating.

To obtain a stable vortex or achieve a similar stable state, the magnetic stirrer was kept rotating at a constant speed to enable the vortex system to achieve a dynamic balance between energy input and viscous dissipation. Ideally, after the vortex stabilizes, the velocity and period of the balls in their respective orbits remain constant. In practice, energy fluctuations are inevitable during dynamic balance establishment, such as minor changes in surface tension affecting intermolecular forces and disturbing energy balance, or unstable energy transfer caused by flow pattern changes during the transition between laminar and turbulent flow. These fluctuations lead to continuous dynamic changes in the balls' orbital radii, increasing the difficulty of precise experimental data measurement.

To address this, two methods were proposed to obtain relatively stable water vortices:

Strategy 1: Trajectory Repeatability Constraint Method In the vortex experiment, the basic condition is set as follows: Balls A and B are started synchronously, and after each completing one circle of motion, both approximately return to their initial positions. Due to differences in motion radius and period, when Ball A finishes its first motion cycle, Ball B is still in the process of its first cycle of motion (with a time difference of about 2 - 10 seconds). In the experiment, the trajectory of Ball A is recorded by an industrial camera, and it is required that the trajectory of its second motion cycle basically coincides with that of the first cycle in space. According to the principles of fluid mechanics, when the energy of the vortex flow field is stable, the motion trajectories of the balls are similar in form; if the energy fluctuates, the trajectories will change. Subsequent comparison of trajectory forms helps screen out experimental samples with relatively stable vortex energy, thereby reducing measurement errors caused by energy fluctuations.

Strategy 2: Energy Conservation Verification Method Assuming that the period of Ball B is longer than that of Ball A, when Ball A shows an increase in orbital radius (R_2) and an extension of the motion period (T_2) in the second motion cycle, the ratio of R_2/T_2 to R_1/T_1 of the first cycle is calculated based on Kepler's third law. If the difference between the two ratios is within the allowable experimental error, it indicates that the total energy of the vortex system remains basically unchanged during this period, and this sample can be used as valid experimental data. This method provides a reliable basis for screening experimental data by establishing the correlation between ball motion parameters and vortex energy states.

3 Experimental Process

3.1 Precalibration

System Calibration

- Adjust the levelness of the experimental platform to ensure the camera's optical axis is vertically aligned with the vortex center, and complete the camera internal parameter calibration using a chessboard calibration plate. (as shown in the figure below)

Calibration accuracy: 0.117mm

- After the calibration process was completed, a systematic measurement verification was carried out on the rectangular standard parts with known reference dimensions (length × width). Through multi-directional dynamic floating tests, a quantitative evaluation was conducted on the dimensional detection accuracy of the visual measurement system. The actual measurement data shows that for the length parameter of the rectangular standard object, the system's measured value is 100.247mm, while its actual reference dimension is 100.303mm. After calculation, the measurement error is controlled at the level of 0.056mm . (as shown in the figure below)

Environmental Control

- Configure a ring-shaped light supplement system to ensure the water surface imaging contrast ratio $\geq 60\%$ and reduce image noise.
- Maintain a constant stirrer rotation speed to keep the water level fluctuation amplitude < 3 mm, ensuring the three balls are basically on the same horizontal plane.
- The water temperature is 28°C , with the dynamic viscosity of experimental water being 0.839×10^{-3} Pa·s and the kinematic viscosity being 0.841×10^{-6} m^2/s .

3.2 Experimental Data Recording and Analysis

Through the video recording of VisionMaster, the central distance data of Ball A (red) and Ball B (blue) at different moments (based on 30 frames per second) were extracted. The typical sampling points are shown in the following table:

3.2.1 Data from the first group of experiments:

Ball A (Red)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵	Ball B (Blue)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵
Start↵	24s17f↵	50.843↵	Start↵	24s17f↵	86.205↵
↵	24s28f↵	50.959↵	↵	24s28f↵	85.249↵
↵	25s14f↵	53.278↵	↵	25s14f↵	84.192↵
↵	25s27f↵	65.052↵	↵	25s27f↵	85.651↵
↵	26s07f↵	74.336↵	↵	26s07f↵	86.429↵
↵	26s21f↵	74.568↵	↵	26s21f↵	87.610↵
↵	27s05f↵	76.123↵	↵	27s05f↵	88.758↵
↵	27s17f↵	76.610↵	↵	27s17f↵	98.756↵
↵	28s15f↵	66.305↵	↵	28s15f↵	95.175↵
↵	28s28f↵	63.382↵	↵	28s28f↵	101.469↵
End of First Period↵	29s10f↵	52.84↵	↵	29s10f↵	95.632↵
↵	29s25f↵	53.498↵	↵	29s25f↵	86.45↵
↵	30s09f↵	48.576↵	↵	30s09f↵	89.033↵
↵	30s21f↵	54.669↵	↵	30s21f↵	84.164↵
↵	31s↵	54.175↵	↵	31s↵	88.865↵
↵	31s22f↵	58.239↵	↵	31s22f↵	89.654↵
↵	32s06f↵	49.964↵	↵	32s06f↵	90.678↵
↵	32s19f↵	46.054↵	End of Period↵	32s13f↵	90.800↵
↵	↵	↵	↵	↵	↵

Parameter Calculation:

Period Determination

- Period of Ball A: $29s10f - 24s17f = 4.767s$ (1 second = 30 frames), so the calculated $T_A = 4.767s$.
- Period of Ball B: $32s13f - 24s17f = 7.867s$, so the calculated $T_B = 7.867s$.

Calculation of R

- Method 1: The pixel coordinates of the small balls were recorded and their trajectories were exported. It can be observed that all trajectories are ellipses approximating circles. Origin software was used to perform circle fitting and ellipse fitting on the trajectories respectively. The former can obtain the radius of the circle, and the latter can obtain the semi - major axis of the ellipse. The radial parameter (R) values obtained by the two fitting methods are close. After comprehensive comparison, since the goodness of fit of circle fitting is higher and the deviation of the center is smaller, the circle fitting results are finally selected. The following are the trajectory fitting graphs of the red ball and blue ball, as well as R_A and R_B derived therefrom.

$$R_A = 540.08251 \times 0.117 = 63.189 \text{ mm (pixel distance} \times \text{pixel accuracy)}$$

$$R_B = 769.1261 \times 0.117 = 89.987 \text{ mm (pixel distance} \times \text{pixel accuracy)}$$

- Method 2: Meanwhile, considering that the arithmetic mean method has good universality and operational convenience in processing irregular trajectory data, the arithmetic mean of multiple measurements was also adopted in the experiment as the characterization parameter of the radial distance (R). This method can accurately reflect the actual characteristics of the movement trajectory of the small balls and provide a supplementary quantitative basis for the experimental data.

$$R_A = 64.027 \text{ mm}$$

$$R_B = 89.70977 \text{ mm}$$

Law Verification(fitting curve):

- Ball A: $R_A^3/T_A^2 = 63.189^3/4.767^2 = 11100 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2)$
- Ball B: $R_B^3/T_B^2 = 89.987^3/7.867^2 = 11770 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2)$

Law verification (arithmetic mean):

- Ball A: $R_A^3/T_A^2 = 11550.57 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2)$
- Ball B: $R_B^3/T_B^2 = 11665.03 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2)$

3.2.2 Data from the second group of experiments:

Ball A (Red)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵	Ball B (Blue)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵
Start↵	1min46s08f↵	76.088↵	Start↵	1min46s08f↵	58.994↵
↵	1min46s27f↵	71.545↵	↵	1min46s27f↵	55.208↵
↵	1min47s06f↵	69.323↵	↵	1min47s06f↵	55.549↵
↵	1min47s16f↵	70.695↵	↵	1min47s16f↵	58.239↵
↵	1min47s28f↵	72.632↵	↵	1min47s28f↵	60.901↵
↵	1min48s09f↵	77.492↵	↵	1min48s09f↵	57.601↵
↵	1min48s22f↵	79.452↵	↵	1min48s22f↵	56.231↵
↵	1min49s04f↵	79.106↵	↵	1min49s04f↵	56.228↵
↵	1min49s14f↵	82.085↵	↵	1min49s14f↵	54.498↵
↵	1min49s25f↵	82.021↵	↵	1min49s25f↵	54.886↵
↵	1min50s08f↵	85.218↵	End of First Period↵	1min50s06f↵	55.338↵
↵	1min50s22f↵	86.052↵	↵	1min50s22f↵	55.543↵
↵	1min51s05f↵	88.834↵	↵	1min51s05f↵	58.210↵
↵	1min51s18f↵	92.347↵	↵	1min51s18f↵	62.549↵
↵	1min52s05f↵	95.392↵	↵	1min52s05f↵	66.214↵
↵	1min52s15f↵	95.053↵	↵	1min52s15f↵	65.213↵
↵	1min53s01f↵	93.627↵	↵	1min53s01f↵	63.882↵
↵	1min53s12f↵	91.809↵	↵	1min53s12f↵	59.986↵
End of Period↵	1min53s25f↵	90.138↵	↵	1min53s25f↵	57.761↵
↵	↵	↵	↵	↵	↵

Parameter Calculation:

Period Determination

- Period of Ball A: 1min53s25f - 1min46s08f = 7.57s (1 second = 30 frames), so $T_A = 7.57s$.
- Period of Ball B: 1min50s06f - 1min46s08f = 3.93s, so $T_B = 3.93s$.

Calculation of R (Arithmetic Mean)

$$RA = (76.088 + 71.545 + 69.323 + 70.695 + 72.632 + 77.492 + 79.452 + 79.106 + 82.085 + 82.021 + 85.218 + 86.052 + 88.834 + 92.347 + 95.392 + 95.053 + 93.627 + 91.809 + 90.138) \div 19 = 83.1$$

$$RB = (58.994 + 55.208 + 55.549 + 58.239 + 60.901 + 57.601 + 56.231 + 56.228 + 54.498 + 54.886 + 55.338) \div 11 = 56.698$$

Law Verification

- For Ball A: $\frac{R_A^3}{T_A^2} = \frac{(83.1 \text{ mm})^3}{(7.57 \text{ s})^2} = \frac{573047.491 \text{ mm}^3}{57.3049 \text{ s}^2} = 10014.1 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2)$
- For Ball B: $\frac{R_B^3}{T_B^2} = \frac{56.698^3}{3.93^2} = 11800 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2)$

3.2.3 Data of the third group of experiments

Ball A (Red)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵	Ball B (Blue)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵
Start↵	23s29f↵	84.791↵	Start↵	23s29f↵	82.477↵
↵	24s14f↵	86.890↵	↵	24s14f↵	82.616↵
↵	24s25f↵	86.304↵	↵	24s25f↵	78.151↵
↵	25s07f↵	84.192↵	↵	25s07f↵	77.147↵
↵	25s21f↵	82.876↵	↵	25s21f↵	81.919↵
↵	26s03f↵	82.999↵	↵	26s03f↵	88.119↵
↵	26s15f↵	81.977↵	↵	26s15f↵	94.797↵
↵	27s↵	80.340↵	↵	27s↵	98.517↵
↵	27s11f↵	79.251↵	↵	27s11f↵	103.479↵
↵	27s23f↵	80.058↵	↵	27s23f↵	103.631↵
↵	28s04f↵	76.158↵	↵	28s04f↵	98.734↵
↵	28s18f↵	73.739↵	↵	28s18f↵	91.840↵
↵	28s29f↵	71.207↵	↵	28s29f↵	84.782↵
↵	29s11f↵	71.376↵	↵	29s11f↵	87.245↵
↵	29s24f↵	71.458↵	↵	29s24s↵	84.139↵
↵	30s06f↵	74.986↵	↵	30s06f↵	81.251↵
End of Period↵	30s12f↵	80.000↵	↵	30s19f↵	81.565↵
↵	↵	↵	End of Period↵	31s06f↵	83.084↵
↵	↵	↵	↵	↵	↵

Parameter Calculation:

Period Determination

- Period of Ball A: 30s12f - 23s29f = 6.43s, so $T_A = 6.43s$.
- Period of Ball B: 31s06f - 23s29f = 7.23s, so $T_B = 7.23s$.

Calculation of R (Arithmetic Mean) $R_A = 79.2 \text{ mm}$, $R_B = 87.97 \text{ mm}$.

Law Verification

- For Ball A: $\frac{R_A^3}{T_A^2} = 12015.7 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2\text{)}$.
- For Ball B: $\frac{R_B^3}{T_B^2} = 13023.4 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2\text{)}$.

3.2.4 Data of the fourth group of experiments

Ball A (Red)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵	Ball B(Blue)↵	Time in Video (30 Frames per Second)↵	Distance from Vortex Center (mm)↵
Start↵	23s12f↵	68.691↵	Start↵	23s12f↵	82.425↵
↵	24s↵	67.103↵	↵	24s↵	81.668↵
↵	24s11f↵	63.076↵	↵	24s11f↵	78.934↵
↵	24s24f↵	61.183↵	↵	24s24f↵	77.432↵
↵	25s03f↵	62.350↵	↵	25s03f↵	78.530↵
↵	25s15f↵	60.572↵	↵	25s15f↵	87.516↵
↵	25s27f↵	58.790↵	↵	25s27f↵	94.212↵
↵	26s11f↵	56.798↵	↵	26s11f↵	99.325↵
↵	26s23f↵	60.699↵	↵	26s23f↵	102.140↵
End of First Period↵	26s27f↵	70.12↵	↵	26s27f↵	108.323↵
↵	27s01f↵	80.414↵	↵	27s01f↵	115.865↵
↵	27s12f↵	70.250↵	↵	27s12f↵	105.359↵
↵	27s24f↵	68.585↵	↵	27s24f↵	111.313↵
↵	28s06f↵	64.555↵	↵	28s06f↵	113.475↵
↵	28s16f↵	64.733↵	↵	28s16f↵	111.342↵
↵	28s29f↵	70.759↵	↵	28s29f↵	114.750↵
↵	29s08f↵	75.701↵	↵	29s08f↵	109.739↵
↵	29s19f↵	82.647↵	↵	29s19f↵	100.440↵
↵	29s28f↵	72.957↵	↵	29s28f↵	97.710↵
↵	30s08f↵	75.733↵	End of Period↵	30s08f↵	83.479↵
↵	↵	↵	↵	↵	↵

Parameter Calculation:

Period Determination

- Period of Ball A: $26s27f - 23s12f = 3.5s$, so $T_A = 3.5s$.
- Period of Ball B: $30s08f - 23s12f = 6.867s$, so $T_B = 6.867s$.

Calculation of R (Arithmetic Mean) $R_A = 62.9382 \text{ mm}$, $R_B = 97.7 \text{ mm}$.

Law Verification

- For Ball A: $\frac{R_A^3}{T_A^2} = 20430 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2\text{)}$.
- For Ball B: $\frac{R_B^3}{T_B^2} = 19770 \text{ (mm}^3/\text{s}^2\text{)}$.

3.3 Experimental Errors

Experimental Group	$\frac{R^3}{T^2} = K$ (Inner Ball)	$\frac{R^3}{T^2} = K$ (Outer Ball)	Relative Deviation
Group 1	11550	11665.03	0.99%
Group 2	10014.1	11800	16.38%
Group 3	12015.7	13023	8.05%
Group 4	20430	19770	3.28%

Table 1: Experimental Data of R^3/T^2 Values and Relative Deviations

Note: The formula for relative deviation is:

$$\text{Relative Deviation} = \frac{|x_1 - x_2|}{\frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}} \times 100\%$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the R^3/T^2 values of the inner and outer balls, respectively, and x is the arithmetic mean of the two values.

- The camera calibration error is 0.211 mm (the camera lens is approximately 50 cm away from the water surface, using a monocular camera).
- When the vortex rotates, there is a slight fluctuation in the water level. Therefore, it is necessary to keep the magnetic stirrer rotating at a constant and slow speed to minimize the water surface drop, and ensure that the centers of the three balls are basically on the same plane to reduce measurement errors.
- In the experiment, the vortex system achieves a short-term dynamic equilibrium between energy input and viscous dissipation. During the equilibrium process, there will be energy fluctuations, which lead to changes in the vortex energy. Consequently, the orbit or period of the small balls will change accordingly. This unstable state is the main cause of errors in the experimental results.
- The Kepler constant of Experiment 2 shows a relatively larger deviation (compared with other groups). This is because there is a significant difference between the starting position (76.088) and the ending position of the first cycle (90.138) of the red ball. Its trajectory presents an open spiral shape accompanied by vortex energy fluctuations, which makes it difficult to accurately determine the cycle time. Therefore, when selecting experimental samples, priority should be given to those where the starting position is the same as or close to the ending position of the cycle.

4 Experimental Summary

The experiment preliminarily verified that the water vortex and the Keplerian system follow a unified central force field vortex dynamics law, i.e., $\frac{R^3}{T^2} = K$. Experiments with fluids of lower viscosity will yield better results.

Experimental observations indicate that there is a significant correlation between the rotational speed of the magnetic stirrer and the energy state of the vortex system: when the rotational speed of the stirrer increases, the angular velocity of the magnetic stir bar increases accordingly, which directly drives the overall rotational speed of the water vortex to increase, and the enhancement of the vortex rotational speed can be regarded as an intuitive characterization of the increase in the system's energy. Specific experimental data show that under the working condition of a rotational speed of 280 revolutions per minute (Experiment 1), the measured Kepler constant K_1 is $11000 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}^2$; when the rotational speed is increased to 310 revolutions per minute (Experiment 4), the corresponding Kepler constant K_4 increases to $20000 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}^2$. The above results reveal that the energy level of the water vortex system is positively correlated with the Kepler constant, that is, the higher the energy of the vortex, the larger the corresponding R^3/T^2 ratio (Kepler constant).

In orbital observations, it was found that while the peripheral spheres perform revolution, they are accompanied by significant spin and precession phenomena. Particularly interestingly, an Earth-Moon system-like composite motion pattern was observed: Ball A orbits along the main track of the vortex center, and Ball B orbits around Ball A as a secondary center. This dynamic behavior exhibits isomorphism with the multi-level motion architecture of satellites-planets-stars in celestial systems.

5 Attachment:

Experiment Video 1 (Recording of the first group's experiment process, corresponding to the data in Table 1):

<https://youtu.be/SwqySjDzqR0>

Experiment Video 2:

<https://youtu.be/LE-pxjY0jzA>

Experiment Video 3:

<https://youtu.be/LE-pxjY0jzA>

Experiment Video 4:

<https://youtu.be/LWo3ST4B0k0>

References

- [1] Kepler, J. (1619). *Harmonices Mundi (The Harmony of the World)*. Johannes Planck Verlag: Linz, Austria.
- [2] Lamb, H. (1932). *Hydrodynamics* (6th ed.). Cambridge University Press: Cambridge.